

INNOVATIVE APPLICATIONS WITH THERMOPLASTIC FILAMENT WINDING TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: Filament winding is one of the most challenging technologies when axisymmetrical or even unsymmetrical composite structural shells have to be produced with continuous fibre reinforcement. This paper presents thermoplastic filament winding techniques which is an advanced method of the standard filament winding process developed for thermosets. It has the potential to overcome the drawbacks of conventional filament winding. It offers the option to achieve consolidation during the process which eliminates the need for any post consolidation processing. Studies found that thermoplastic filament winding can be more cost effective than thermoset winding.

Thermoplastic filament winding generating three dimensional shapes with continuous reinforcement following the load paths will be discussed in this paper. The feasibility of this technique is demonstrated by discussing experimental results and applications.

KEYWORDS: filament winding, thermoplastic, direct flame processing head, bicycle frame, electric motor, pressure vessel

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composite materials offer a number of advantages as high fracture toughness, unlimited shelf life, recyclability, and continuous processing by avoiding the curing cycles which are characteristic for thermoset matrix composites. In addition to favourable mechanical properties thermoplastics offer a wide range of manufacturing options. Recent interest in advanced thermoplastic composites has been spurred by the promise of higher manufacturing productivity, increased quality and improved material properties.

PROCESSING HEAD

One promising thermoplastic processing method is the direct flame filament winding. Therefore a unique thermoplastic direct flame (TDF) winding head has been developed.

For direct flame processing (Figure 1) of thermoplastic matrix filament wound composites the tape supply, the tape brake and process control system are mounted on the support of the filament winding device. The TDF winding head including the heat source is installed on the

swivel axis. A mechanical brake is used to provide constant tape tension to achieve good consolidation.

Fig. 1: Thermoplastic direct flame (TDF) processing scheme

The universal TDF winding head can easily be retrofitted to existing winding machines without any additional investment (Figure 2). The capability of the winding head has been demonstrated by manufacturing of various applications as described in this paper. Winding angles between 0° and 90° were realised. Any commercial tape material can be processed. The application of the compaction shoe is optional and depends on part geometry and winding angles.

Fig. 2: TDF winding head positions

The TDF winding head incorporates a direct flame torch which gives the energy input to the tape achieving in-situ consolidation. In order to prevent matrix degradation if the winding process stops, the direct flame torch is attached to a pneumatic swivelling arm. The torch is in parking position during the process stops and turns into working position as soon as the winding process starts again.

The main objective is to generate an adequate melt zone of the thermoplastic matrix to obtain proper bonding between tape and consolidated laminate. This can be managed by focusing the flame and melting the matrix on the top surface of the laminate and the surface of the incoming prepreg tape simultaneously. The torch is directed exactly to the contact point.

BICYCLE FRAME

Composite bicycle frames for high-performance sports are predominately manufactured by filament winding or roll wrapping using thermosetting matrices. First attempts to use thermoplastic matrices speak in favour of this replacement. The main arguments for the introduction of thermoplastic composites into the road and racing bike market are: inherent vibration damping characteristics, high impact resistance, low environmental emission during processing, greater ease of recycling, possibility of thermal post-forming, absence of curing cycles and unlimited storage life of the semifinished products [1, 2].

Fig. 3: Thermoplastic filament wound bicycle frame

On the basis of manufacturing bicycle frames it is demonstrated that thermoplastic filament winding is a challenging approach for producing high-quality structural components. Finite element analysis was used to design two different bicycle frames, a conventional diamond-frame (Figure 3) and a frame with a suspending rear arm. Prototypes of both frames were manufactured using a soft flame process. Winding angles down to 17°, wall thicknesses

between 1.0 mm and 2.4 mm and speeds up to 8 m/min were realised working with a cold mandrel. In order to obtain smooth surfaces, an improved post processing technique using a compression belt was applied. Determination of the damping behaviour indicate that using thermoplastic reinforced tubes the damping properties can be improved by 8% versus thermoset tubes [3].

ELECTRIC MOTOR

The reinforcement of a 1,5 MW electric motor is manufactured using the TDF winding process (Figure 4). Such electric motors drive the German ICE trains. The electric motor incorporates 2 hoop wound rings, directly wound on the short circuit rings.

The maximum power of the electric motor was about 1 MW at 4000 revolutions per minute without the reinforcement. After increasing the number of revolutions the short circuit rings deformed unacceptable. By reinforcing the rings with carbon fiber reinforced polyetheretherketon (CF/PEEK) tape using the direct flame tape laydown the number of revolutions has been increased up to 6000 which results in 1,5 MW power. The testing of the motor in conjunction with optical microscopy indicates that high quality is achieved.

Fig. 4: Reinforcement of a electric motor

LOW PRESSURE VESSEL

Filament winding can make a significant contribution to fuel economy by reducing the dead weight of steel containers that are currently used as fuel tanks, air supply for hydraulic accumulators, operating hydraulic valves, etc.. For such applications the feasibility of using

TDF winding in conjunction with PP/GF tape (Trade name: PLYTRON® / Supplier: Borealis) was proven by fully overwrapping a blow moulded liner (Figure 5).

The structure of the reinforcing laminate of the pressure vessel was designed and programs for the computer numerical controlled winding process were developed. To demonstrate feasibility, samples of different vessel types were manufactured on a seven-axis gantry winding machine.

The vessels were hydraulically tested. The target burst pressure of 40 bar from the full composite vessel was exceeded by 22 %. The full composite vessel reduces the dead weight of a steel vessel by 55 % and enhances the safety failure mode [4].

The investigations show, that TDF winding offer new possibilities in manufacturing full composite pressure vessels.

Fig. 5: Helical winding of fiber reinforced thermoplastic tape with TDF head

HIGH PRESSURE VESSEL

Thermoplastic reinforced composite pressure vessel for storage of compressed natural gas (CNG) are available on the German market. They are made of oil-quenched and tempered chromium-molybdenum powder coated steel, reinforced with an aramid fiber in the cylindrical section.

Such cylinders are used as gas storage for city buses. 7 gas cylinders (each has a volume of about 165l) are fixed on the roof of the bus (Figure 6) and operate at a pressure of 200bar which gives a operating capacity of 300 km [5]. The light weight cylinder is used in order to increase the driving behaviour of the bus without changing the bus design.

For manufacturing such light weight CNG cylinders the unique thermoplastic direct impregnation (TDI) process has been developed. The main objective of this development is to reduce the material costs by impregnating the fibers during the winding process. First experiments using the TDI process (Figure 7) show that reasonable impregnation quality can be achieved.

Fig. 6: Compressed natural gas (CNG) cylinder with hoop wound fiber reinforced thermoplastic tape

Fig. 7: Thermoplastic direct impregnation (TDI) processing scheme

CONCLUSION

This paper illustrates important methods for processing thermoplastic composite materials by filament winding. On the basis of various applications it is demonstrated that thermoplastic filament winding is a challenging approach for producing high-quality components.

A thermoplastic direct flame (TDF) winding head which can easily be retrofitted to all existing winding machines has been demonstrated.

Bicycle frames were manufactured using carbon fiber reinforced polyamide tubes with winding angles down to 17°, wall thicknesses between 1.0 mm and 2.4 mm. In order to obtain smooth surfaces, a patented post processing technique using a compression belt was applied. Electric motors were reinforced in order to increase the number of revolutions and full thermoplastic pressure vessels were manufactured by helical winding of glass fiber polypropylene tape. Also a thermoplastic direct impregnation (TDI) process has been developed in order to hoop wind light weight CNG cylinders.

All these investigations confirm, that thermoplastic winding offers new possibilities in manufacturing light weight components.

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